

INFLUENCE OF RAW MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS ON THE PULP MOLDING PROCESS

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Abstract: *Due to the negative impact of fossil-based, plastic packaging on the environment and the demand for sustainability, the molded pulp industry has been growing tremendously in recent years. The sustainable qualities of these packaging materials, as well as certain government regulations and the growing customer demands for a more 'green packaging', is making companies eager to find suitable alternatives to those currently used oil-based forms of packaging. Molded pulp packaging is produced from biodegradable lignocellulosic fibers like wood-based fibers, hemp fibers or other fibrous materials, therefore, it became focus of research and gained importance in industrial applications. Although molded pulp packaging is a rather old technology, as it has been around for over a hundred years now, scientific understanding of the whole process and the needed material properties is incomplete. Here, an overview of the different production procedures will be given. Furthermore, first results of measurements obtained for the so-called thermoforming process will be presented. The goal of this work was to emphasize the importance of understanding the characteristics of the used raw materials in order to optimize the molding process. For this reason, different types of fibrous materials, which are already being used in pulp molding processes and their characteristics, like the lignin content, fiber length distribution, ash content and drainage level, have been compared.*

Keywords: molded pulp, lignocellulosic material, material properties, sustainable packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

Plastic and their related products are common due to their light weight, high performance, low cost and ease of processing. People have become addicted to disposable plastic and the proliferation of plastic products in the last decades has been extraordinary (Zhang et al., 2022).

Since the usage of fossil-based, plastic packaging is increasingly considered unsustainable, the demand for environmentally friendly, biodegradable packaging is growing. Furthermore, the increasing awareness of the population regarding the negative impact of plastic packaging is one of the main driving forces for research and development in the field of “green packaging” materials and technologies (Jacobsen, Pedersen and Thøgersen, 2022). One of green and sustainable packaging materials, molded fiber and its products have attracted increasing amount of attention due to its recyclability, renewability, biodegradability and sustainability (Didone and Tosello, 2019; Zhang et al., 2022).

According to the International Molded Fiber Association (IMFA), the whole pulp molding process can be split into four sub-group technologies. These are thermoforming, transfer molding, thick-wall molding and processed molding:

- Thermoforming: This is the most established production process in industry. The molded parts are formed in four steps: first, the molded form is captured in a heated mold, then it is getting pressed, densified, and, finally, dried. The greatest advantage of this technology is that additional oven curing is not needed. The obtained forms are of high-quality, with rather smooth surfaces and walls with thicknesses ranging from 2 mm to 4 mm.
- Transfer molding: For this technology, a forming mold and a transfer or take-off mold, as well as a drying oven, are required. The molded forms have wall thickness between 3 mm to 5 mm with smooth surfaces on both sides.
- Thick-wall molding: During this molding process an open mold is used, and the molded forms are dried in an oven. The forms, which are typically made from a mixture of Kraft and recycled paper, have two different surfaces – the inside surface is rather smooth, while the outer side is very rough. The thicknesses of those forms can range from 5 mm to 10 mm.

- Processed molding: Already produced molded pulp forms that need special treatments, like additional coatings, printing or additives are belonging to this category. (Didone et al., 2017)

Historically, the molding technology already dates back to 1890 and the early 1900s, where the first patents by Keyes (Keyes, 1903, 1904) appeared. Even though, molded pulp packaging was already used in daily life, since egg cartons were produced with the molding process, the first technologies were not described until 1966 by Emery (Emery et al., 1966). Now, over 40 years later, molded pulp packaging is still a very popular packaging material for electronic devices, eggs, beverages and is used as support material for transport protection of various devices as well (Didone et al., 2017). Despite its application for such a long time, there is little knowledge available on how the raw materials must be prepared to guarantee a smooth production process. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the raw material characteristics and, to be even more accurate, the fiber properties, since they can have a big impact on the production process and the final product properties. That is why in this work, different raw materials, which are currently used for the production of molded pulp packaging, were analyzed. It is important to have knowledge of the characteristics of the raw material, like the lignin content, refining degree and the ash content in order to adapt the whole molding process including the parameters accordingly. Furthermore, depending on this, decisions for the need of additional devices, like a refiner or deflaker, or supplementary agents, like retention aids, can be made.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Raw material

The raw materials used for the measurements in this study are already utilized for the production of molded pulp packaging with the thermoforming process. In this work, samples of corrugated cardboard, grey board, chemical pulp and different kinds of coated cardboard of type GC1 and GC2 (labelled as A GC1, B GC1 and A GC2) from different suppliers were used. GC1 means that it is a pigment coated virgin mechanical pulp board with a white reverse side and GC2 is the same board type but with a cream reverse side.

2.2 Kappa number

The Kappa number serves as a measure of the relative hardness, the bleachability or the degree of the pulping process. With this method, the determination of residual lignin present in the pulp is enabled. The basis of the Kappa number measurement, according to Tappi Method T 236 om-13, is the reaction of

potassium permanganate (KMnO_4). It is a strong oxidizing chemical which reacts with lignin and a small amount of other organic impurities remaining in the pulp (Czibula, 2021).

2.3 Refining degree (Schopper Riegler)

The refining degree (SR°) was determined after the procedure of Schopper Riegler according to DIN EN ISO 5267-1. The obtained value from the measurement indicates the drainage rate of a defined volume, namely 1000 mL of an aqueous pulp suspension, through a fiber cake which forms on the sieve during the test (Blechsmidt, 2013; Mandlez, 2017).

2.4 Ash content

The ash content, which is basically the ash residue of the sample, was determined according to DIN 54370 and ISO 1762. It is the residue, given in weight percentage, remaining after burning either a paper or pulp sample at a specified temperature until the weight is constant. Depending on the sample nature, different annealing temperatures of 525°C, 575°C, or 900°C are used. In our case the method was applied at 525°C (paper and cardboard samples) and 575°C (chemical pulp sample). The obtained values serve as a guide, but are not a quantitative measure of the real amount of inorganic components in a sample (Blechsmidt, 2013).

2.5 Fiber analysis

In order to characterize the different kinds of raw materials, morphological Fiber Tester measurements were conducted to know the fiber shape (curl), the fines content and the average fiber length. For this, the L&W Fiber Tester Plus device from ABB (Zürich, Switzerland) was used to analyze fiber dimensions, as well as the fiber form, from which the mean kink-index and kink-angle were acquired.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measured raw material characteristics, like the Kappa number, Schopper Riegler, ash content and pH-value are summarized in Figure 1. The Kappa number as well as the pH-value were only measured for the coated A GC1 and A GC2 pulp board. Here, the comparison between those two materials was important since they were behaving quite different during the molding process. One type of the coated pulp boards was leading to a high frequency of machine blockages and foam formation and it was believed that the root for this cause might be in a

difference of the fiber properties. However, the measurements proofed that these two materials are very much alike in view of the parameters tested.

Figure 4. Summary of the raw material characteristics: Kappa number [-], Schopper Riegler [SR], ash content [%] and pH-value [-] as used in the pulp molding process. A GC1, B GC1 and A GC2 are the samples of different types of pigment coated virgin mechanical pulp board.

The results of the raw material characteristics (see Figure 1) are also showing that the grey board contains the highest amount of inorganic components, like fillers, with 24.2% while the used chemical pulp has little to no ash content with 0.15%. The corrugated cardboard and the coated pulp boards are comparable, but it is obvious that the sample A GC2 has a much lower ash content. The reason for this could be the non-coated reverse side of this product.

Besides the raw material characteristics, it was important to gain knowledge about the morphological fiber properties, which are presented in Figure 2. The results of the measurements are indicating that the used raw materials are varying not that much from each other, except for the fibril area. Since the chemical pulp was not refined, it is containing the longest fibers but is having the lowest percentage of fibrillated area with only about 0.8 %, while the fibrillated area of the other materials is ranging between 3.4 to 6.7%. For some packaging geometries the unrefined fibers are advantageous, since they contribute the most to the geometric stability of the packaging. The other fiber morphology values, like the curl , the mean kink-angle and kink-index are very similar for all the samples.

Figure 5. Summary of the measured fiber properties obtained with the L&W Fiber Tester Plus: fines content [%], curl [%], mean kink-angle [°] and kink-index, as well as the fibrillated area [%] and the length and width of the different raw materials used for the pulp molding process. A GC1, B GC1 and A GC2 are the samples of different types of pigment coated virgin mechanical pulp board.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Here, the basic properties of raw materials used for the pulp molding process were presented. They should set the base for further understanding the whole molding process, especially the thermo-forming process, to optimize the whole production technology. With the knowledge of the different characteristics of the raw materials and how they perform in the process, ideal mixtures to produce customer-specific molded packaging forms can be determined.

The results of the fiber properties have shown that a certain fiber length distribution of the fiber suspension is necessary to have the molding process running smoothly without having blockages or quality losses in the products. However, fiber properties like curl, mean kink-angle and kink-index were very similar for all the raw materials, therefore, they are not considered to affect the process. Another important parameter is the ash content of the used raw material, because if the content of inorganic residuals is high, retention aid is needed to retain these small particles to diminish the material losses during the process, and to improve the process water quality.

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